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Liberty, Affect, and The Rise of Populism¹

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ABSTRACT

In this essay, I reinterpret Hartley B. Alexander's early 20th-century account of liberty and democracy in light of the 21st-century populist resurgence, integrating the economic analysis of Jonathan Hopkin and Mark Blyth. By combining Alexander's concerns surrounding the ethical collapse of democratic citizenship with Hopkin and Blyth's diagnosis of structural economic disenfranchisement, I construct a dual account of populism's rise as the convergence of moral atrophy and institutional decay. From Trump's America to Modi's India, populism emerges as a liberty weaponised against itself. I argue that populism is a condition wherein the form of democracy is preserved, but its substance is debased, thereby reduced to spectacle, demagoguery, and institutional dysfunction. Drawing on specific examples and institutional analysis, I further argue for a reconstruction of liberty grounded in moral formation and institutional responsiveness, thus offering a normative pathway beyond the populist condition.

“We cannot say of a man who can exercise his will and reason only when they are in accord with a more authoritative will and reason, that he is a free man; we cannot regard that citizen whose highest activity is as mouthpiece or tool of the state, as a free citizen.” - Hartley B. Alexander from “Liberty and Democracy” (1917), p.140.

Introduction

The global ascendancy of populism—expressed through moralised grievance, institutional distrust, and the concentration of political identification in charismatic figures—raises a pressing philosophical and political question: what does democracy mean when the people, as a political abstraction, are turned against democratic institutions? Which in turn brings about a second question: what becomes of liberty when it is invoked against the very institutions that once sustained its possibility? To address these, I argue that populism is not merely a deviation from democracy but its internal crisis, a dialectical reaction to liberty's progressive severance from both ethical discipline and institutional mediation. To trace this crisis, I reconstruct and synthesise two seemingly disparate but convergent lines of thought: Hartley Burr Alexander's (1917) metaphysical theory on democratic liberty, articulated in “Liberty and Democracy,” and Jonathan Hopkin and Mark Blyth's (2018)

¹ I would like to thank Geoffrey D. Callaghan for his early contributions to this essay. The ideas herein were shaped, in part, by our conversations at the University of Windsor in early April 2025.

structural critique of economic disenfranchisement in “The Global Economics of European Populism.”

Alexander’s early 20th-century writing, often overlooked in contemporary democratic theory, presents a vision of liberty not as a natural right or spontaneous expression of the will, but as a moral achievement—a cultivated disposition grounded in self-restraint, rational judgment, and civic virtue. For Alexander, liberty without ethical formation is not merely fragile; it is self-destructive. When democratic life is driven by unmediated affect rather than institutional reason, the demos ceases to be a source of sovereignty and becomes, instead, a vehicle for collective irrationality. This condition Alexander describes anticipates what later theorists would call mass politics or the tyranny of the majority. His warning, therefore, is that the democratic state, precisely because it disperses power, is uniquely susceptible to becoming a conduit for unreflective will, unless it is grounded in institutions that cultivate character and sustain judgment.

Building upon and extending this moral foundation, I introduce Hopkin and Blyth’s political-economic framework as the structural mirror of Alexander’s philosophical concerns. Where Alexander identifies liberty’s moral deterioration, Hopkin and Blyth uncover its material dislocation. They argue that the institutional architecture of post-war democracy has been systematically dismantled by decades of neoliberal reform; that is, the liberalisation of capital flows, fiscal retrenchment, the de-politicisation of central banks, and the weakening of labour protections. These processes, they contend, have not only exacerbated inequality but have also eroded the meaningfulness of democratic participation. Populism from this angle is not cultural pathology or irrational resentment, but a structurally coherent—if politically regressive—response to the collapse of democratic responsiveness. It is the expression of a populace that finds itself increasingly governed without influence, represented without recognition, and included only as a statistical abstraction.

Methodologically, I advance a dialectical synthesis that is both normative and diagnostic. It reads Alexander and Hopkin/Blyth not as case studies to be juxtaposed, but as conceptual interlocutors whose insights, when integrated, offer a comprehensive theory of liberty’s unravelling in contemporary democratic regimes.

The method unfolds in three layers. First, it reconstructs Alexander’s metaphysics of liberty as an ethical condition, situating it within a civic-republican tradition that links freedom to moral personality and institutional form. Second, it mobilises Hopkin and Blyth’s empirical findings to expose how institutional disembedding—through neoliberal globalisation and technocratic depoliticisation—has rendered this ethical conception of liberty materially unsustainable. Third, it synthesises these perspectives into a dialectical theory of populism as the political consequence of liberty’s decoupling from its conditions of realisation; that is, moral cultivation and reciprocal recognition.

My central claim is thus not that populism represents a departure from liberty, but rather that it is liberty’s own distorted expression—a form of ethical and political inversion. Populism appropriates the language of self-rule and sovereignty while dismantling the institutional and moral infrastructures that make those ideals liveable. The leader becomes the vessel of popular expression, but without mediation, deliberation, or accountability; the people are affirmed in rhetoric but denied substantive agency in governance. This, I argue, is not simply authoritarianism in populist garb; it is the symptom of a deeper ontological shift in the status of liberty itself. When institutional credibility collapses and the moral personality of the citizen is no longer formed through civic education or participatory structures, liberty does not disappear; it mutates. It becomes affective, identitarian, and oppositional. That is to say, it becomes a call to reclaim power, not to govern justly, but to punish, to restore, or to purify.

This diagnosis requires a reconsideration of the prevailing assumptions in both liberal and populist thought. The liberal tradition, with its emphasis on procedural fairness and negative liberty, often presumes that democratic institutions can function without sustained investment in moral culture or economic inclusion. Populist responses, on the other hand, treat liberty as a right to immediate expression, ignoring its dependence on shared norms, structured deliberation, and institutional restraint. Both, in different ways, fail to grasp liberty's relational ontology: that it is neither a possession nor a discharge of will, but a socially constructed capacity emerging through practices of recognition, judgment, and self-limitation.

To address this failure, the final section of the essay develops a constructive response. Drawing on examples from participatory budgeting, civic education, and institutional co-governance, I argue for a dual reconstruction, first, of democratic institutions as sites of genuine agency, and second, of civic culture as a space for ethical formation. Liberty must be reclaimed not as spontaneity, but as a disciplined practice of shared self-rule. This means transforming institutions from administrative apparatuses into arenas of meaningful participation, and reorienting public education toward the cultivation of reflective, self-governing citizens. Without these, the dialectic of populism will persist—ever oscillating between resentment and submission, expression and disenchantment.

This essay, therefore, contributes to democratic theory on three levels. First, it retrieves and reinterprets an overlooked metaphysical foundation for liberty in the work of Alexander. Second, it integrates structural political economy into normative democratic theory, showing how material dislocation undermines moral agency. Third, it advances a novel thesis: that liberty, once decoupled from ethical and institutional grounding, becomes its own undoing, fuelling a form of political will that undermines the very conditions of its legitimacy. Populism, in this view, is not the enemy of democracy, but its unresolved contradiction; a distorted mirror reflecting what liberty has become when stripped of the scaffolding that once sustained it.

Liberty

At the outset, it would be imprudent not to define what I mean when I write of liberty herein. Understandably, there are many interpretations of liberty, and my definition is by no means exhaustive. What it is, is one in keeping with Alexander's conception, and to that aim, I believe it to be concise.

Liberty is the ontological structure of rational agency—a power of self-determination that inheres in the capacity of a mind to interrupt immediacy, suspend impulse, and choose reflectively between real alternatives. It is not instinctual, affective, or spontaneous, but deliberative and *spiritual*. As Alexander (1917: 143) writes, “the essence of true freedom is rational choice,” and reason itself “acts through judgments” which “are always decisions between possible alternatives.” Liberty, then, is not a faculty parallel to reason, but reason exercised as freedom; a dynamic form of inward activity that actualises itself through the responsible adjudication of competing courses of action.

In metaphysical terms, liberty is not a property of the will abstracted from context, nor an innate human right; it is the condition under which the will becomes intelligible as ethical. It emerges not from negation (the removal of constraint), but from affirmation (the self's willingness of itself in accord with a principle higher than its own immediacy). It is not reducible to choice per se, but to rightly ordered choice. That is to say, choice responsive to reason, not merely preference. Liberty, for Alexander (1917: 148), “is the delicate equilibrium of life, and like all life it is a state of individual

souls”—it is neither instinct nor command, but the spiritual medium through which the person relates to law, justice, and truth as self-chosen obligations.²

Thus, liberty is the actuality of reason within the *soul*—it is what it means for judgment to become being. It is not the rejection of constraint but the reflective power to legislate one’s own conduct in light of a good that transcends private desire. It exists only where the mind is sufficiently detached to reflect and sufficiently formed to will what is rationally discerned. In this way, liberty is not a freedom *from* but a freedom *into*—into responsibility, into universality, into shared moral existence.

The Dislocation

At the heart of Alexander’s political metaphysics lies a suspicion of liberty disengaged by ethical discipline. Far from espousing a romantic or utopian vision of democratic freedom, Alexander identifies liberty as a moral achievement—not a given, but a task. As he notes, the ideals of liberty and democracy are metaphysical ideals; therefore, they cannot be made concrete in human institutions save through the intelligence and virtue of men (Alexander, 1917). Liberty, on this account, is not a natural entitlement but a cultivated condition. It is realised not through the absence of constraint, but through the presence of character—an internalisation of self-restraint, judgment, and moral self-governance.

This conception leads Alexander (1917: 145-46) to a prescient concern: that liberty, once severed from its moral foundations, becomes self-destructive. The democratic state is peculiarly exposed to the *despotism of passion*, he warns, and this is not a critique of human emotion per se, but of the political elevation of unmediated affect into the principle of rule (Alexander, 1917: 145).³ In Alexander’s analysis, when collective passion displaces institutional reason, democracy becomes indistinguishable from mob rule—Alexander (1917: 145) calls this “social absorption.”⁴ The danger lies not in public engagement, but in the unreflective mass—unrestrained by virtue, unmoderated by institutions—transforming popular sovereignty into a tyranny of sameness. As he nods, the state is, first of all, the protector of the person—the individual man, the “rational expression”—against the mass (Alexander, 1917: 139). In this vision, freedom is not atomistic or Lockean; it is civic-republican, requiring a mediating institutional order that protects individuality from absorption into collective frenzy—“rational expression of the nation [...] should rule as our human reason should rule our lesser faculties” (Alexander, 1917: 139).

Alexander’s metaphysics thus implies an anthropology. Human beings are not born free; they *become* free only through moral formation. Political liberty, accordingly, is not a precondition for virtue but its institutional expression. Institutions—schools, legal systems, political parties, public

² Alexander’s reference to the “soul” (and my reference to it insofar as liberty is in part “spiritual”) should not be read theologically, but metaphysically, as the locus of rational activity and moral selfhood. The soul, in this sense, names the inward structure of the self, capable of reflective judgment, not merely the seat of emotion or belief. It is that in man which can stand apart from immediacy, deliberate between ends, and bind itself to principle. As such, liberty as a state of the soul refers to the actuality of reason within the self. That is to say it is the self’s power to determine its action not by impulse or external compulsion, but by thought directed toward the good.

³ I offer ‘despotism of passion’ as a distilled and faithful articulation of Alexander’s position.

⁴ Alexander contrasts the excellence of mind with what he calls “social absorption,” emphasizing that rationality emerges through individual detachment rather than collective identification. My claim—that collective passion displacing institutional reason turns democracy into mob rule—articulates this concern in political terms: when democratic institutions are overtaken by collective fervor, they lose the reflective distance necessary for rational governance, collapsing into the very mob mind Alexander (1917: 144-45) deems “infinitely less rational” than the individual.

forums—must foster the conditions under which self-governance can emerge. When they fail to do so, liberty degenerates into license, and democracy into populist despotism (Alexander, 1917: 148).

Hopkin and Blyth's political economy offers a complementary critique from the opposite direction. Where Alexander charts the moral precariousness of democratic liberty, Hopkin and Blyth diagnose its structural dislocation. Populism, they argue, is not simply a cultural backlash but a materially rational response to a political-economic order that has rendered democratic participation all too close to meaningless—that is, economic marginalisation of the majority of voters (Hopkin and Blyth, 2018: 218-19). This marginalisation is not accidental. It is the consequence of decades of policy regimes—capital mobility, financial deregulation, labour market flexibilization, and fiscal austerity—that systematically eroded the post-war democratic compact.

Consider the global scope of this dislocation. Between 1980 and 2023, the share of national income accruing to the top 1% increased by over 10 percentage points in the United States, for the top 10% in the United Kingdom from 1980 to 2016, just over 7%, and in India from 1980 to 2018, 27% (World Inequality Database, 2023). Real wage growth for middle- and lower-income earners stagnated, while returns to capital soared. Labour's share of income declined globally, and social safety nets were dismantled under the guise of fiscal responsibility. The result was the depoliticisation of economic life: major policy levers—monetary policy, trade regimes, investment decisions—were placed largely beyond the reach of democratic deliberation (Hopkin and Blyth, 2018: 212).

These trends have not abated. In the third quarter of 2023, the OECD (2024b) reported that real household income per capita declined in 10 out of 21 countries for which data were available, despite GDP growth. These numbers only marginally levelled out (with GDP) by the end of the fourth quarter, with only 6 out of 19 countries showing a decrease, while 2 remained flat (OECD, 2024a).⁵ Meanwhile, the Edelman Trust Barometer (2024) shows that only 51% of respondents across 28 countries have trust in their government, rising only one percentage point in 2025. For example, in the United States, Gallup polling from 2024 shows trust in the government is “below its average dating back to 1972, with several near their historical low ratings” (Brenan, 2024). These trends speak to the decoupling of economic performance from lived experience. However, as of February 2025, Gallup polling indicates that the approval rating of the United States Congress stands at 29% from 20%, the highest in just over two years (Brenan, 2025; Gallup, 2025b). These data point to two things: institutional legitimacy continues to weaken across advanced democracies—not due to ignorance, but due to a perceived collapse in reciprocal recognition—and the rise of populism sees in some instances a parallel rise in trust (discussed in more detail to follow).

Despite the temporary regaining of trust, underlying such trust is structural disenfranchisement—one which echoes Alexander's concern, though its genealogy is economic rather than ethical. The despotism of passion that Alexander (1917: 137) fears is here reinterpreted as reactive, not innate—a political response to decades of institutional betrayal.⁶ Individuals no longer trust the democratic process, not because they are irrational, but because the system no longer reflects their agency. The populist appeal to reclaim sovereignty is therefore not a mere manipulation of the crowd, but a symptom of a deeper loss of reciprocal recognition. And therefore, populist leaders, by presenting themselves as the voice of the people against these types of betrayals, perform a kind of inverted legitimacy—a parody of representation that speaks to the very real void in democratic responsiveness.

⁵ In both quarters the United States saw some of the largest discrepancies according to OECD statistics.

⁶ Betrayal is an emotion, but in the democratic context it signals a deeper normative failure—the state's abandonment of its telos: to mediate collective will through just institutions. The feeling reflects not only loss, but the violation of a promise inherent to democratic legitimacy.

From this vantage point, populist figures are not just demagogues; they are the embodiments of failed institutional mediation. They symbolise the breakdown of the moral-institutional ecology that makes liberty possible. Populism, then, is not an irrational deviation from democracy—it is the rational articulation of democracy’s hollowing-out. And the passions it mobilises, I argue, are not raw instincts but politicised grief: the fury of a demos abandoned by the institutions meant to represent it.

Crisis of Recognition

The convergence of Alexander’s moral diagnosis and Hopkin and Blyth’s structural analysis yields the notion that modern populism is not merely a crisis of policy or political representation but a philosophical event—a collapse in the moral and institutional conditions that render liberty both intelligible and livable. Populism does not simply reject elite authority; it undermines the distinction between rule and impulse, and governance and grievance, which makes authority ethically coherent. In this respect, both Alexander and Hopkin and Blyth (collected) suggest that populism is the political form taken by liberty once severed from institutional restraint and moral cultivation.

Alexander’s (1917: 144) suggestion that democracy without ethical culture becomes the most lawless of tyrannies—of chief concern: the “organised mob”—may initially seem a relic of moralistic idealism. Yet, when placed alongside Hopkin and Blyth’s account of economic disenfranchisement, the remark gains empirical weight. Ethical culture, in Alexander’s (1917: 132) sense, is not reducible to manners or moralism but consists in the sustained effort to subordinate impulse to principle—a discipline that both requires and generates institutional trust. When this trust is systematically reduced—when democracy without choice becomes the norm—the conditions for such ethical cultivation evaporate.⁷ Rational participation gives way to reactive affiliation. The populist subject, far from being a citizen in the classical sense, is cast as an injured agent, animated by a deep moral grievance against a system that no longer sees or serves them.

This moral grievance, however, is not a path back to ethical community. Populism offers a simulation of sovereignty rather than its restoration. The populist leader personalises the voice of the demos but offers no mediating structure through which the people can govern themselves. In this sense, the populist promise is inherently contradictory. It elevates immediacy over mediation, passion over deliberation, and identity over autonomy. Thus, as Alexander (1917: 137) foresaw, the democratic state exposes itself to the despotism of passion, but that passion today is not strictly emotional excess; it is the structured result of the same institutional betrayals mentioned earlier.

Hopkin and Blyth’s emphasis on the disembedding effects of neoliberal globalisation pragmatically situates this point. The numbers are stark: by the eve of 2022, the top 1% globally captured 38% of total income growth, while the bottom 50% received only “a frightening” 2% (Chancel, 2022: 3). In the United States the share of national income going to the top 10% increased from 33.8% in 1980 to 46.8% by 2023, while simultaneously, wage growth for the bottom 50% has stagnated and even declined in inflation-adjusted terms (World Inequality Database, 2023). This rising inequality is not simply about outcomes but about participation. As Hopkin and Blyth (2018: 198) note, once parties stopped offering policy alternatives, political agency narrowed into identity performance. The breakdown is thus both disruptive and democratic. Voter turnout in the U.S. fell among working-class populations between 2000 and 2016, while upper-income participation rose—a trend that continued into the 2020s (Laurison and Rastogi, 2023). And the gap in voter turnout, according to the Institute for Public Policy Research (2025), between those with and without university degrees

⁷ Democracy without choice describes a posture that preserves electoral form while emaciating substantive alternatives. In other words, real alternatives vanish as power is centralized. This is, in part, maintained through delegitimizing opposition through rhetorical means, thus, subverting the ethical conditions (i.e., reflection) of democratic life.

has widened in the UK in 2024 to double what it was in 2019, and between homeowners and renters by 19 percentage points between 2017 and 2024.⁸ The democratic subject has been attenuated not by apathy but by structural exclusion.

The nation-state, once the principal of political agency, has separated in part from its economic levers. Capital mobility and fiscal retrenchment have constrained governments' ability to respond to public demands. As of 2024, the average statutory corporate tax rate around the world—across 181 jurisdictions—is 23.51%, down from 40.18% in 1980 (Tax Foundation, 2025; OECD, 2023b). This decline in corporate tax rates has severely restricted national capacity for redistribution of public investment. Consequently, promises of responsive governance ring inadvertently insincere.⁹ Hopkin and Blyth's (2018: 213-15) diagnosis that neoliberalism creates forms of democracy without choice becomes plainly visible: the material instruments of autonomy—education, housing, secure employment—are increasingly inaccessible. The further insight, then, is that liberty—understood as moral and political autonomy—requires a scaffolding that is neither spontaneous nor self-perpetuating. I argue it must be cultivated through both individual ethical discipline and structural inclusivity. Alexander understood the former; Hopkin and Blyth expose the decay of the latter. Their analyses intersect precisely where liberty collapses—the moment institutions meant to secure personal moral development and collective decision-making are no longer seen as credible or responsive.

Indeed, the populist uprising is not simply an assertion of the will of *the people* against elites. It is the attempt to recover a lost moral reality, albeit in a distorted form. The leader's appeal is existential, not just economic. He appears to restore meaning, identity, and recognition to a public that has been abstracted out of politics. But the mechanism of this restoration is anti-political, for (in many cases) it bypasses deliberation, negates opposition, and sacrifices pluralism for unity. What results is not the reconstruction of the demos but the enthronement of a spectral collective—a people-without-institution, animated by resentment and represented by a figure who is above law because he is presumed to embody it.

Alexander's anthropological pessimism thus anticipates the condition that Hopkin and Blyth empirically describe. The citizen, for Alexander, is not a natural unity but an ethical achievement—the individual is a moral personality and the law of his own conduct. And therefore, in order for such self-rule to flourish, institutions must support the individual in becoming capable of judgment. In contrast, the populist turn operates by collapsing this process. For it arguably exploits unformed judgment, misdirected anger, and tenuous trust, transforming them into instruments of mass assertion. Thereby leading not to empowerment but symbolic compensation for lost autonomy.

The scale of this can be seen in the decline of institutional trust across democracies. For instance, in the U.S., trust in Congress fell from 42% in 1973 to just 7% in 2014, according to Gallup polling (Rayman, 2014). Trust in the presidency declined from 52% to 23% from 1973 to 2022 (Elliott, 2022). Trust in the federal government declined from 35% in 2022 to 23% in 2024, a drop that, according to the Partnership for Public Service (2024), reflects a broader breakdown in civic engagement. As the report notes, when “the points of interaction between [...] government and the public deteriorate [...] a fundamental disconnect emerges between Americans and the only institution in the country with the resources, responsibility and authority to serve all” (Partnership for Public Service, 2024). This decline is not isolated, but shared globally, where across the OECD, confidence in national

⁸ The inclusion of these specific statistics is to show the changes in structural and material aspects of arguably the most prone demographic to populism: the working-class.

⁹ I say this charitably, on the grounds that those who may be implementing structural changes in this way may also very well be those who are uttering promises. In that case, my charity (using the term “inadvertently”) comes into play. This assumes structural changes and promises are done with genuine benefit in mind instead of a designed means-ends calculations, i.e., purposeful instrumentalization.

governments fell to under 38% by 2022 (OECD, 2023a). These numbers signal more than disillusionment—they reflect a withdrawal from the ethical labour of judgment that Alexander sees as essential to democratic life. Institutions no longer command trust because they no longer appear to mediate between principle and power. Populism fills the vacuum by dispensing with mediation altogether.

Where Alexander warns that law becomes mere force when it is not seen as the manifestation of the rational will, Hopkin and Blyth show how neoliberal technocracy disarticulated that rational will from political life. Fiscal constraints, independent central banks, and global trade treaties often bypass democratic input, producing depoliticised decision-making (Johnson, 2006; Jones and Matthijs, 2019). This is a rule without responsibility, I argue—authority without accountability. In such conditions, populist anger is not only understandable but, in a sense, philosophically correct, for it registers a rupture in the normative order that makes political authority legitimate. Yet it resolves that rupture not through ethical reinvestment or institutional renewal, but through the projection of sovereign will onto a single figure—a surrogate for agency.

These dynamics reveal populism's tragic character. It begins with a demand for meaning, for justice, for recognition, but ends by annihilating the very structures through which these can be realised. It is, in Hegelian (1977) terms, a form of *unhappy consciousness*, oscillating between rebellion and submission, demanding moral coherence while dismantling its preconditions. The leader appears as the master but is in truth the slave of the crowd's injured moral impulse. And the people, in turn, confuse catharsis with empowerment, expression with authority, and reaction with rule.

Liberty in reversal

This dual failure—of ethical cultivation and institutional mediation—explains the global character of contemporary populism. In each case—Trump's America, Modi's India, Erdoğan's Turkey, and Orbán's Hungary—we see the fusion of Alexander's fear and Hopkin and Blyth's diagnosis: a morally disoriented public responding to a materially dislocated state. What distinguishes these populisms is not a shared ideology but a shared structure—the disintegration of the conditions that make liberty both intelligible and sustainable.

Donald Trump's America provides perhaps the clearest case of this structural-moral convergence. His call to “drain the swamp” was not a technocratic critique of inefficiency, but a moral indictment. The political class was portrayed as not simply ineffective but ethically bankrupt—a sign that the moral covenant between the state and its citizens had been violated. This narrative reframes disenfranchisement as betrayal and anger as virtue. Trump's performance of authenticity—his rejection of political decorum, his aggressive rhetorical style, and even his personal vulgarity—functioned not in spite of his elite status, but because of it. His wealth became a symbol of incorruptibility, and his demagoguery, a performance of radical transparency.

The empirical background to this rhetoric reveals its structural exclusion. Since the 1970s onward to 2015, the real hourly wages of American workers have increased by only 0.2% per year, while productivity has grown at over 1.33% annually (Bivens and Mishel, 2015). This decoupling of labour and reward created a surplus of resentment that populist rhetoric could moralise. Juxtapose this decoupling with the optics of the top 0.1% of U.S. earners owning more wealth than the bottom 90% combined (Saez and Zucman, 2014). And finally, add the collapse of political trust—Gallup polling from 2022 shows confidence in Congress at 7%, the Supreme Court at 25%, and the presidency at 23%—and the populist proposition becomes rational: the institutions that were supposed to secure liberty now appear as obstacles to it (Elliott, 2022; Jones, 2022). In this context, it is telling that as of May 18th of this year, a president with approval ratings 16% below the 87-year average for two-

term presidents is nonetheless polling 20% higher than 2022 levels of trust in the presidency as an institution (Gallup, 2025a).¹⁰

Alexander's warning—the despotism of passion—finds its realisation not in mob violence per se, but in the moral transvaluation of resentment into civic virtue. The checks and balances that form the ethical architecture of liberal democracy are recast as deep state conspiracies, elitist obstructions, or unaccountable bureaucracies. Populist movements thus seek to recover liberty not by strengthening institutional mediation but by bypassing it altogether—what Hopkin and Blyth might call a promise to restore sovereignty by circumventing deliberative constraint. In this bypass, liberty becomes indistinguishable from unmediated will.

A parallel structure appears in Modi's India, where liberty is expressed not as participatory autonomy but as majoritarian assertion. The ruling Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) has fused Hindu nationalism with economic aspiration, presenting Modi as the embodiment of both cultural authenticity and developmental authority. Here, the enemy is not a corrupt elite per se, but a pluralist tradition that once enabled institutional dissent. The judiciary, the press, and the academy—once seen as mediating organs—are rebranded as enclaves of anti-national sentiment. As of 2025, India ranks 159 out of 180 countries on the World Press Freedom Index, a decline from its position at 133 in 2016 (Reporters Without Borders, 2024). Simultaneously, the government has passed legislation weakening judicial independence and targeting dissenting academics (International Commission of Jurists, 2025).

The political logic is unmistakable: liberty is weaponised not to include but to exclude, to define *the people* not through procedural recognition but through cultural purification. The Citizenship Amendment Act of 2019, which fast-tracks naturalisation for non-Muslim refugees, exemplifies this. It formalises the exclusion of a religious minority under the banner of national renewal. The ethical function of liberty—to recognise and safeguard difference—is reversed. Alexander (1917: 148) warned that something akin to liberty without intelligence is where virtue becomes license, and in Modi's India, that license is conferred on majoritarian desire, converting the moral vocation of freedom into an instrument of cultural domination.

Similar patterns appear in Erdoğan's Turkey, where his populist regime has progressively knocked the bottom out of institutional independence while maintaining the symbolic form of democracy. In Turkey, constitutional reforms in 2017 shifted the system from parliamentary to presidential, granting Erdoğan sweeping powers. The judiciary has since been purged; over 4,000 judges and prosecutors were dismissed after the failed 2016 coup (Stockholm Centre for Freedom, 2017). Press freedom (Freedom Press Index) has plummeted—Turkey ranks 165 out of 180 in 2024—and opposition leaders have faced frequent arrests (Reporters Without Borders, 2024). This institutional atrophy is paired with a performative appeal to sovereignty, tradition, and unity. Erdoğan routinely positions himself as the protector of the Turkish family, the Islamic faith, and the national economy—all against the imagined conspiracies of Western liberalism and internal dissent. As with Trump and Modi, the populist leader becomes a synecdoche for the people. His power is justified not through deliberative legitimacy but through moral embodiment. And the state then, once a site of mediation, becomes an extension of will.

Hungary under Viktor Orbán is perhaps the most refined iteration of populist anti-liberalism. Orbán's strategy has been to reframe democratic norms as elite fictions masking cultural decay. In

¹⁰ The apparent discrepancy between institutional trust and presidential approval arises from a distinction in polling categories. Trust in the presidency refers to public confidence in the office as an institution, irrespective of who holds it, whereas presidential approval gauges support for the individual currently occupying the role. Thus, a decline of institutional trust (Elliot, 2022) can coexist with a relatively stable approval rating for a particular president (Gallup, 2025a).

2014, he declared his ambition to build an *illiberal democracy*, one that rejects multiculturalism, judicial independence, and open society values. This project has been remarkably successful. However, the Freedom House (2025) rating for Hungary fell from what was then the highest possible ranking of 1/7 in 2005 to 65/100 in 2025, with press freedom and judicial independence identified as areas of sharp decline.¹¹ Orbán justifies these regressions through a moralised defence of Hungarian identity. Opposition to immigration, LGBTQ rights, and EU integration is cast not as intolerance but as fidelity to national essence. The form of liberty is preserved—elections are still held, parties still compete—but its substance is all but wanting. As in Alexander’s (1917: 137) warning, liberty becomes indistinguishable from the tyranny of sameness, or more pragmatically, a “tyranny of public opinion.” Leading therefore to the sentiment that there is only one people, one culture, one voice, and dissent—even when legal—is cast as treasonous or foreign.

This global pattern reflects a philosophical crisis: the collapse of liberty as an ethical-political form. In each case, populism arises as a distorted response to real exclusions. It offers not false grievances, but false solutions. The political leader becomes the medium through which structurally abandoned populations imagine themselves as re-empowered. But this empowerment is reactive, not constructive. It does not build institutions; it abrades them. It does not cultivate autonomy; it simulates it through identification. The result is a political condition in which the form of freedom is maintained—through elections, rhetoric, and symbolic appeals—while its substance is evacuated.

Populism is not merely authoritarianism in disguise; it is liberty turned against itself.¹² It is what happens when the ethical preconditions for autonomy are replaced by moralised grievance, and the institutional structures of mediation are replaced by charismatic projection. The result is not simply *unfreedom*, but the paradox of a society that claims to speak freely even as it loses the very capacity to deliberate, to dissent, and to decide.

In this way, we return to Alexander’s (1917) deepest concern that liberty is not the natural state of individuals but the fragile outcome of ethical discipline and institutional coherence. The fact that populism now flourishes across such diverse cultural and economic contexts suggests that the problem is not local but ontological. It is not merely that particular democracies have failed, but that the moral and structural conditions for liberty are being globally undermined. What remains is a ghost of freedom—still invoked, still performed, but increasingly empty in content and corrosive in effect. Thus, to respond to populism, one must go beyond technocratic adjustments or procedural reforms. One must reconstruct the dual scaffolding that Alexander and Hopkin/Blyth both diagnose as broken; that is, the internal formation of ethical judgment and the external formation of democratic capacity. This means rebuilding institutions that are not only procedurally fair but substantively empowering, and thereby capable of fostering autonomy through inclusion, deliberation, and moral trust.

The challenge is formidable. As Hopkin and Blyth emphasize, the economic foundations of democracy have been systematically enfeebled. Yet without such foundations, Alexander reminds us, the moral subject cannot form. It is here that philosophy becomes political once more—not by prescribing policies, but by illuminating the conditions under which persons can become agents and citizens can become sovereign. What emerges, then, is a shared task to recover liberty not as license

¹¹ In 2020 Freedom House moved from the “Democracy Score” (of 7) and shifted to “Democracy Percentage” (of 100).

¹² More precisely, my claim is that populism is a political logic that pits a morally pure people against a corrupt elite, claiming exclusive representation of the general will. However, when populist leaders reject institutional constraints (and thereby are free from them) and pluralism (an implicit form of checks and balances) in the name of that will, they often slide into authoritarian practices as neither of those buffers are existing.

or reaction, but as the disciplined practice of moral and political self-rule. Populism, in this light, is not our future; it is our warning.

Restoring liberty's promise

The way out of the dialectic exposed herein is neither a nostalgic return to elite governance—a making of anything *great* again—nor an uncritical embrace of populist immediacy. Both fail for the same reason, that is, they treat liberty as either a possession of the few or a mere reaction of the many. In contrast, liberty must be reconstructed as a dual process—moral formation and institutional responsiveness—unified by the idea that freedom is not simply the absence of constraint, but the capacity for judgment under conditions of mutual recognition.

This requires a re-theorisation of democratic participation not as the expression of desire, but as the cultivation of public judgment. As Alexander (1917: 147-48) implied, the problem of liberty is not solved by allowing more people to express themselves, but by enabling them to reflect on what their expression means, entails, and demands of others.

First, institutions must be reformed to reflect and reinforce democratic agency. As Hopkin and Blyth (2018: 221) allude, if citizens are to trust political institutions, they must see that political choices matter. This begins with reversing the depoliticisation of key economic domains. According to Blyth (2015), the deregulation of finance and the rise of capital mobility led to highly profitable banks and the decline in interest rate spreads, causing banks to take on riskier investments and increasing leverage, which contributed to the 2008 financial crisis where liquidity evaporated, shifting power from labor to finance (Hopkin and Blyth, 2018: 200). This liquidity—unmatched by any civic institution—renders national decision-making to appear impotent, even when formally democratic.

To restore agency, policies that have placed markets beyond democratic oversight must be reevaluated. These include not only capital liberalisation and privatisation, but also the institutionalisation of austerity via constitutional amendments, independent central banks, and trade regimes that override domestic legislation. For example, according to the IMF (2023) analysis, the euro area's fiscal constraints under the Stability and Growth Pact have contributed to public investment rates remaining subdued, with many member states investing at or below around 3% of GDP, and in some cases falling under 2% of GDP. This arguably limits the ability to respond to local needs effectively.

An oppositional logic is evident in institutional innovations like participatory budgeting—now practised in over 3,000 municipalities worldwide—which have shown measurable impact. A World Bank study found that such practices in Brazil led to increased health spending, lower infant mortality, and higher tax compliance (Gonçalves, 2014). Likewise, local economic councils, as piloted in Spain and across other parts of the EU, have allowed communities to guide investment priorities, match training programs to regional employment needs, and integrate marginalised populations into decision-making.¹³ Cooperative enterprises—particularly in sectors like renewable energy, agriculture, and banking—offer another form of democratic economic governance. In the U.S., credit unions and cooperatives account for more than \$3.7 trillion in assets as of December 2023, often delivering more stable outcomes during economic downturns (Toomer-McAlpine, 2024).

Such reforms reposition institutions as sites of democratic learning. When citizens can see, shape, and share in the consequences of political decisions, they begin to regard democracy not as a

¹³ Examples of these types of projects are Lan Ekintza Bilbao in Spain and the EU's LEADER (Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale) and CLLD (Community-Led Local Development) programs.

transaction but as a project. This reconstructs legitimacy not through charisma or ideology, but through involvement.

Second, the culture of democracy must be reanimated through education, public discourse, and civic practice. Alexander's insistence on the cultivated individual must be reinterpreted not as a defence of elitism, but as a call for ethical pedagogy. In an environment saturated by commodified media, algorithmic manipulation, and declining public trust, the very capacity to deliberate is under threat. For example, as of 2024, 57% of Americans report getting their news primarily from social media, and 86% say they do "at least sometimes" (St. Aubin and Liedke, 2024). These platforms, designed not for reflection but for engagement maximisation, I argue, undermine the conditions for collective judgment. To counter this, public education must be reoriented around civic reasoning and philosophical reflection. Critical media literacy, political economy, and ethical deliberation must be treated as core democratic competencies, not optional supplements. A curriculum in which students are asked to examine not only how systems function but also why they should exist, and in whose interest, is essential. As Alexander (1917) nods: no man is truly free unless he governs himself through reason. The task is not simply to inform citizens but to equip them with the intellectual and moral habits that allow self-governance to be more than a slogan.

This also means investing in deliberative public forums, such as citizens' assemblies and town-hall processes with binding consequences. Ireland's Citizens' Assembly on abortion law reform demonstrated how structured deliberation—facilitated, informed, and plural—can address polarising moral issues with reasoned consensus. The OECD (2020) report *Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions* points towards this reliance on citizens' assemblies and other deliberative processes, showing these effects were strongest where outcomes had tangible legislative weight.

Importantly, this dual project resists both the technocratic impulse to manage democracy from above and the populist urge to collapse it into pure immediacy. It affirms that liberty is not reducible to the vote, nor to the market choice, nor to expressive venting. It is instead, a social achievement—an ongoing practice—sustained by institutions that empower judgment and individuals trained to exercise it. In this way, the reconstruction of liberty is neither nostalgic nor quixotic. It begins in the small acts of institutional redesign and educational renewal that build, over time, the capacities democracy needs to survive. For liberty is not the raw assertion of will; it is the mediated, reflective exercise of judgment in relation to others. It cannot, therefore, be preserved by suppressing desire, nor by amplifying it, but only by transforming it—through education, reflection, and structured participation—into public reason.

What is required, then, is not just more democracy, but better democracy. A democracy thick with meaning, grounded in daily life, capable of cultivating citizens who can distinguish resentment from justice, and freedom from license. Without this reconstruction, we will remain trapped between two failures: that is, the elite who cannot justify their rule, and the people who cannot rule themselves. Between them, in the interval, liberty decays.

Closing Remarks

I have argued that populism is not the negation of democracy but its tragic recognition—a desperate cry for liberty in a world that no longer offers it. In this sense, it is neither anomaly nor aberration, but the dialectical return of what liberal democracy has forgotten: the ethical and institutional preconditions of its own legitimacy. Alexander anticipated this danger a century ago, warning that liberty unmoored from moral development collapses into passion without principle. Hopkin and Blyth chart the structural dimension of this collapse—how the disembedding of markets from democratic control erodes the material foundations for political agency. Taken together, these two

critiques illuminate populism not as an external threat, but as liberty turned against itself—seeking sovereignty where none remains, and agency where it has been hollowed out.

This argument has unfolded through a dual-track analysis. First, the moral: liberty, as Alexander makes clear, is not a natural possession but a disciplined acquisition, a rational expression of self-mastery achieved through ethical cultivation and institutional support. Political liberty is intelligible only when mediated through structures that foster judgment, deliberation, and civic responsibility. Once these mediating institutions degrade, or the conditions for self-governance evaporate, liberty transforms into its opposite: not freedom, but the assertion of unreflected will. This is the root of social absorption—a democratic degeneration in which individuality is eclipsed by unrestrained collective passion, and where reasoned dissent gives way to mimetic affirmation.

Second, the structural: Hopkin and Blyth’s analysis of neoliberal globalisation demonstrates how economic policy has systematically hollowed out the institutional infrastructure necessary for liberty’s enactment. The mobility of capital, the erosion of labour protections, the depoliticisation of monetary policy, and the constitutionalization of austerity have all contributed to a situation in which key levers of public power are insulated from democratic deliberation. This results not only in material inequality, but in a deeper form of disenfranchisement: the disappearance of meaningful agency within the formal apparatus of democratic governance. Citizens, rendered spectators to political economy, become disoriented subjects of resentment. Populism arises not in the absence of political desire, but in the absence of political reciprocation.

The second-order result of this synthesis is a conceptual reframing of populism as neither wholly pathological nor authentically emancipatory. Rather, it is the form liberty assumes when it has been detached from both of its sustaining grounds: that is, ethical formation and institutional inclusion. Populism, in this view, is structurally rational but normatively unstable. It arises from legitimate grievances but channels those grievances through a mode of identification that bypasses the very institutions through which agency might be restored. The populist leader becomes the performative vessel of a demos denied reciprocal recognition. His authority derives not from deliberative legitimacy but from affective proximity, from his ability to project the appearance of representation without the substance of governance.

This reimagined dialogue points toward a thesis for consideration: global populism is the dialectical consequence of liberty’s internal contradiction—its tendency to become anti-political when detached from both reciprocal recognition and institutional mediation. In the absence of institutions that reflect democratic agency and the absence of a culture that forms ethical judgment, liberty ceases to function as a condition of self-rule. Instead, it becomes a weapon of resentment. That is, it is a will to assert, not to deliberate—to dominate, not to govern. When neoliberal rationality corrodes the demos, democracy loses its meaning as a collective project and becomes, as Wendy Brown (2015: 128) terms it, an “empty signifier” or ritual of expression.

Thus, populism is not a rejection of democracy, but its afterimage—the echo of political agency in a depoliticised world. It arises when the form of freedom remains, but its substance is gone. The demand for liberty endures but finds only its simulation. Populism is the symptom of this contradiction—a revolt against managed democracy that mistakes expression for emancipation.

Yet this dialectic is not terminal. Its very articulation reveals the path forward. The findings of this essay show that populism’s emergence is intelligible and its mechanism identifiable. It is not a rupture from democratic history, but a predictable expression of liberty’s degeneration in the absence of moral and institutional scaffolding. This means that it cannot be answered by technocratic recalibration alone, nor by moral denunciation. Its resolution requires the reintegration of the very elements whose collapse gave rise to it.

If liberty can degenerate into domination when isolated from virtue and representation, then its rehabilitation must proceed through their reintegration. That is to say, liberty must be reclaimed not as a possessive right, but as a relational achievement. It is not the unconditioned freedom to act, but the capacity to participate in a shared moral world, mediated by just institutions. This calls for a democratic culture thickened by reflection and structured by reciprocal accountability. It requires institutions that do not merely administer the will of the people but cultivate it.

This reframing has philosophical and political implications. It calls into question the liberal premise that liberty is prior to the political. And instead, it suggests that liberty is constituted through the political, through the norms, institutions, and practices that sustain mutual recognition. This reflects somewhat Hegel's (1977: 111; 520) conception of freedom as being with oneself in the other, where autonomy is not isolation, but self-realisation through reciprocal ethical life (*Sittlichkeit*).

What's more, it challenges contemporary democracies to reconceive participation not as atomised preference aggregation, but as moral development. The restoration of liberty thus demands both institutional redesign and civic pedagogy. Without the former, liberty remains unrealizable; without the latter, it becomes unrecognisable. Only by addressing both poles of this dialectic can we begin to reconstruct the conditions of democratic life.

In sum, the findings of this essay reveal the structural and moral logic of populism as the degraded afterlife of liberty. Its legitimacy stems from real exclusion; its form from false resolutions. To resist populism solely as pathology is to ignore the truth it distorts. To embrace it as an authentic expression is to romanticise resentment. The task ahead is harder: to read populism as a bitter epiphany—liberty's recognition of its own incompleteness. And to answer it, not with retreat or celebration, but with a politics that honours liberty's promise by securing its ethical and institutional foundations.

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